

The Secret held in Maputo, Mozambique

Comparing the 200,000 year old ruins in Maputo and Bakoni, South Africa, with the Ramesses stele data, and Gas Giant diameter ratios to look for EPEMC identifications and an improved cosmology over the Tellingier “alien” hypothesis

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ABSTRACT

Though the record of the Egyptians is considered first rate, and that of the Hopewell is extraordinary in their earthworks, what one needs is a web of evidence from around the world. Outside of the giant spheres of Costa Rica, which have yet to be measured, the author had not observed other overt references to the gas giant gods, as they are seen in EPEMC. However, the work of Michael Tellingier in exposing the allegedly 200,000 - 250,000 year old Maputo, and the similar site of Bakoni in South Africa, as a lost city, has brought an excellent opportunity to examine both the enhanced ability of EPEMC to explain infamous OOPArt iconography in a non-pseudoscientific format (such as aliens), and to improve the position over the already weak mainstream archaeological argument, which has no explanation at all.

If a concordance of the Cosmic Egg motif and sky god archetype is proven to exist worldwide, it will fundamentally change the narrative about the cosmology of the Solar System by precluding the present (untenable) accretion model. The world’s myths all speak of a war of the gods, which has been ignored by the mainstream, or sidestepped through Jungian psychological mumbo-jumbo. However, in the altstream there is only two possibilities: an alien war of politics (as purported by the Hindus and Middle Easterners), or planet discharge and solar system rearrangement, as supported by Veliovsky, Talbot, Cardona et al.

Keywords: Ramesses stele - Saturn - Jupiter - Neptune - Maputo - Bakoni

Text from the last paper included for ease of reference:

“Egyptian Record

On the Ramesses stele (dating according to the mainstream of Egyptology to the 1200s BCE [or as old as 2,494 BCE]), it says the following,

*“The gracious god directed Ramesses, the lord of the upper, and of the lower world, the ‘sun’, the director of truth, approved of the ‘sun’, the lord of **diadems**¹, Ramesses, beloved of Amun², the giver of life, like the ‘sun’ forever, Har-Hat, the giver of life, of stability, and of power. A gift of incense and libations. Har³ - **of the two solar abodes**, of life, of stability, and of power, the giver of victory and of magnanimity; like the ‘sun’, continually.”⁴ (emphasis added, see Figure 1)*

Figure 1 - Stele of Ramesses left near the Sphinx, with selected highlights

¹ Clear indication that the first ‘sun’ is Saturn. This text indicates the transfer of power from the previous lord (Saturn/Osiris) to the son, (Jupiter/Horus). This puts doubts to the stele relating to the pharaoh Ramses, who was probably named after this event, but at the end of the Jovian rule in the sky. Rather, it would point to the era following the Great Flood or less likely, before it. However, the stele could also be a memorial of re-creation and an affirmation of holy authority of the nobility, hearkening back to the original transfer of power from father to son.

² Saturn

³ Probably an early rendition of Horus.

⁴ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Rfd9pFEbZA0>

X: 0.4852

Y: 0.393

Note measurements are slightly cropped on stele

Please note the 3 highlighted selections of the tablet (although more are worthy of discussion).

In A is our primary depiction of the Cosmic Egg motif, our “solar” orb, which is definitely of different equatorial and polar diameters. The ratio of X to Y will be measured with a caliper so as to be within 5% accuracy. Comparisons with Figure 2 and 3 ratios will also be made in Table 1.

In B we see the Egyptian depiction of the Great Man/Giant Man/Running Man with a clearer depiction of the torus under the arm. More information about this Thunder God⁵ (here the representation of the “Power” mentioned in the script) can be found in the author’s previous works⁶ and in Talbott^{7 8 9} & Cardona¹⁰.

In C we see a reinforcement of the collinear alignment, as well as a clear depiction of two imperfect spheres, one of which is also slightly larger than the other. A comparison with actual Jupiter:Saturn diameters will be made in Table 2.

There are many other worthy motifs upon this stele, including a large number of confirmations of the importance of thunderhawks, which supports the Native American religious assertions. However, they are not the subject of this analysis. Readers should study the stele for more evidence.

Figure 2 - Stele of Pharaoh Ramesses II; credit: Wikipedia

X: 0.799

Y: 0.694

⁵ [21]

⁶ [15] & [4] & [6]

⁷ “The Saturn Myth”

⁸ <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=5AUA7XS0TvA>

⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=svfWvSHh4AY&list=PLwOAYhBuU3UeFB-ygaH63Seg6r6C_dtqB

¹⁰ “God Star” (series of books)

Figure 3 - Stele of Chia (scribe of Ramesses II)

X: 0.861

Y: 0.692

Table 1: Comparisons of X/Y ratios of 3 stele

	<i>Ramesses Stele</i>	<i>Ramesses II</i>	<i>Chia Stele</i>	<i>Average</i>
X	0.4852	0.799	0.861	0.715
Y	0.393	0.694	0.692	0.593
X:Y	1.23	1.15	1.24	1.21
Stand_Dev	5.11%			

Jupiter, Saturn, and Solar Diameters

The sun (sol/Apollo) is notoriously spherical¹¹, despite gravitational models¹² which should depict it otherwise¹³. In Table 2, its measurements will be presented in km accuracy, for X:Y comparisons.

By contrast, Saturn¹⁴ and Jupiter¹⁵ are notoriously *un-spherical*, and are rather oblate or ovoid¹⁶. The X diameter is ~ 10% larger in Jupiter and 6% larger in Saturn than the Y diameter (pole to pole), which represents very well the effect of kinetic rotation and angular momentum of liquid metallic hydrogen or other fluids and gases. The difference being, primarily, that the sun appears to be composed of crystalline plasma (a form of condensed matter)¹⁷, and actively receiving charge from the Galactic Electric Circuit (GEC), whereas the Jovian and Saturnian brown dwarfs are continuously powering down¹⁸, now starved of GEC supply since being enveloped in the sun's powerful solar wind. However, the arrival of Apollo/Marduk/Set is not the discussion of this paper. For more interest in this stellar electric physics, see the work of W Thornhill¹⁹.

Discussions of the end of Saturn's time as a brown dwarf can be found in the author's previous works²⁰ or the Nahuatl legends of the Mayans²¹.

What is pertinent, rather, is the diameters in Table 2, and their comparison to Table 1 ratios.

Table 2: Solar, Jovian, and Saturnian Comparisons and Standard Deviations

	Sun (km)²²	Jupiter²³	Saturn²⁴	Ratio J:S
X	1,391,982.8	142,984	120,536	1.186234818
Y	1,391,972.8	133,709	108,728	1.229756824
X:Y	1.000007184	1.069367058	1.10860128	
C_X		0.259	0.2475	1.046464646
C_Y		0.245	0.224	1.09375
C X:Y		1.057142857	1.104910714	
Stand_dev		0.86%	0.26%	
Avg C & Real		1.063254958	1.106755997	
Stand_dev vs. Stele		10.38%	7.30%	

¹¹ <https://www.theguardian.com/science/2012/aug/16/sun-perfect-sphere-nature>

¹² <https://physics.stackexchange.com/questions/208344/why-is-the-sun-almost-perfectly-spherical>

¹³ <https://www.scientificamerican.com/gallery/well-rounded-sun-stays-nearly-spherical-even-when-it-freaks-out/>

¹⁴ <https://sos.noaa.gov/datasets/saturn/>

¹⁵ http://www.answers.com/Q/Why_are_Jupiter_and_saturn_not_spherical

¹⁶ <https://spaceplace.nasa.gov/planets-round/en/>

¹⁷ Or the "surface" is a plasma sheath and the real sun is underneath.

¹⁸ As evidenced by their climate change, the dying Red Spot, and the changing color of Saturn's poles

<https://www.space.com/34508-saturn-north-pole-hexagon-color-change.html>

¹⁹ https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=Kff_ytg0-8w

²⁰ [15]

²¹ <http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

²² <https://www.space.com/17001-how-big-is-the-sun-size-of-the-sun.html>

²³ <https://space-facts.com/jupiter-diameter/>

²⁴ <https://nineplanets.org/saturn.html>

Please note C_X and C_Y are caliper measurements from Figure 1, and may have margins of error that cover 1-5% variation. Some errors may be due to computer rendering and/or penciling copy error from the original.

The standard deviations from C and the reality of Jupiter and Saturn make it clear, however, that the stele in Figure 1 clearly depicts Egyptians had line of sight knowledge of the gas giants. Their precision-based culture, with its emphasis on machining and civil engineering, enabled them to measure the diameters and depict them accurately to within less than 1% deviation in either case.

The ratios of X:Y, and of the real measurements taken by satellites leave little doubt as to the identity of the subject in A of Figure 1, and that is Saturn. Therefore, the stele depicts the passage of the power of the God from the father (Saturn/Kronos/Ra/Osiris) to the son (Jupiter/Zeus/Amun/Horus-Har). Hence “approved of the lord of diadems” (Saturn’s rings), and this would then confirm the date of this stele is *most likely* antecedent to 2000 BCE, probably closer to 3500-4000 BCE. It also confirms the hypothesis that the ancients could see the gas giants at least at night.

Please note the final standard deviations are compared with the average from Table 1, and not specifically with the stele of Figure 1. As the planets likely wandered closer and further away, the Egyptians own measurements would probably change, or again the carving may be less precise. The further is more likely applicable as the machining techniques of the ancient Egyptians is well documented to be extraordinarily precise.²⁵

Maputo: Aliens or Record

Assuming that Michael Tellinger is not merely promoting the scientifically validated as ancient sites in Mozambique and South Africa to sell books, it is a curious thing that he pushes the Sitchinesque cosmology when these sites are so obviously stone age sites. He might say, “Well yeah the aliens kept people ignorant and enslaved, so they could mine for gold.”

But there’s nothing in the Sumerian record to suggest that the Adamu and Igigi were actually kept in total stone age abject poverty. Rather, they were raised up, taught literature and farming, and encouraged to participate in politics and commerce. This seems to the author to be a form of cosmogony, rather than a discussion of high-tech aliens. In fact, other than the “ME” referred to - which *may* have been some data storage device - the glaring lack of references to what we would recognize as high technology in Sumerian and Babylonian society is probably an excellent proof via absentia that it is not aliens being described, but anthropomorphized spheroids whose erratic orbital movements were interpreted by bored societies into ancient “star wars” stories, such as the Mahabharata. So how much less likely is the most ancient of sites around the world to be high tech related?

Take the Bosnian pyramids, very obviously shaped hills chosen for shapes and geometry, modified with an early form of concrete and extensive tunneling... It is absolutely unreasonable to assume that the pyramids there are some form of “Stargate” or alien ship receiving space station!

Rather, it is clearly an attempt to worship the Cosmic Mountain/Hill archetype and motif, which is absolutely connected to the Saturnian worship of the Atlantean and Tepi Periods. More to the point, if we *know* that Saturnian worship existed in the early days of Egypt, why should we not assume it did before? Of course we should, and should look for stone age evidence, and find ways to verify it, rather than leap to pseudoscientific hypotheses which can neither be proven *nor disproven* (the hallmark of science is in disproving things!)²⁶

²⁵ “Lost Technologies of Ancient Egypt,” by C. Dunn

²⁶ Be sure to review the author’s comparisons and contrasting of EPEMC and ancient alien architect hypothesis. https://www.academia.edu/37856134/Ancient_Alien_Architect_Hypothesis_and_EPEMC_Brief

So when we look at the Maputo and Bakoni sites without apriori assumption that *only* aliens could have created these sites, or their slaves, then we can look for the other alien sky: the original Zep Tepi sky, pre-rearrangement of the Solar System!

Figure 4 - Excellent view of the human shaped hill and its sloped backside²⁷

Figure 5 - Ancient Architect theory of Star Gates and purposes of Pyramids²⁸

²⁷ Clearly used for approaching the Creator Saturnian God for worship.

²⁸ Sitchin implied (or inferred in his 'translations') that the pyramids were commemorations of power and family in regions of gold harvesting.

Measuring up Maputo & Bakoni

Maputo (and Bakoni) have numerous rock strewn geometric sites which have, from an EPEMC perspective, excellent rock-art “peer” evidence of solar system re-arrangement data, which show *potentially* the very end of Ooranus and birth of the 4 gas giants: Jupiter (Zeus), Saturn (Kronos, then Hera), Neptune (Poseidon & Shiva), and Uranus (Hades/the Devil being punished and sent to the Underworld for rebelling).

As will be shown in the measurements (see Tables), the data shows that this object had an equatorial:polar diameter ratio of 1.21 to 1.25, and must have occurred in the Tepe or Archaic period of ancient Egypt, **not 200,000 - 250,000** years ago. It must be the same event that ended the Tepe period ~7,000 - 12,000 YBP. This event may have initiated the Younger Dryas clusters, rearranging planetoids which could have shattered and come into proximity of Earth, or brought the Moon from Jupiter (as should be assumed based on the Enuma Elish), bringing the remains of Kingu and Tiamat’s “army” to hit the Earth in clusters, and potentially again later (mostly with electrical thunderbolt storms, but also physically with “thundereggs”). The event must have been an entire series of interesting cosmological events, perhaps instigated by the approach of Marduk (the sun or Jupiter, it isn’t clear), but which ultimately resulted in the “castration” (of Venus and Mars as testicles) of Saturn, turning Kronos into a female “sister” of Zeus, and the removal of Earth to Jupiter’s orbit, rather than Saturn’s (probably Kronos was the core remnant of Ooranus, or Re). It, unfortunately, isn’t clear what instigated this event, but the god Apollo was apparently quite distant at the time, as he later “grew like a baby” as the Earth left Jupiter and moved closer, causing a period of “Frost Giants” which has been evidenced in flash freezing of mammoths with unfossilized food found in their stomachs in the Siberian tundras.

In reconstructing this, then, we seek to test three things:

1. Concordance with the Ramesses and other stele
2. Identification, via diameter ratios (DR), of the ovals at Maputo and Bakoni, and therefore which Period we can expect the site to be verified by mainstream scientists (and so predicting as a test of EPEMC)
3. Disclusion of hypotheses and bad data, especially in discussion of the origins or cosmogony of the solar system, and Earth’s place in it, as a result of its rearrangement due to the “Flare God” event²⁹.

In the vein of that, therefore, we will use the same method (and scans of the selections will be given for scientific verification of data) of caliper and ruler (for large enough diagrams/photos from above) to generate ratios. And rather than focus on standard deviation, we will use % difference³⁰ to look for 1%, 3% and 5% boundary conditions for best, great, and good evidence (in that order). Some notes about technique:

1. Location of measurement nodes are done by eye, meaning using the author’s judgment of the most important location to indicate the furthest average/good extremes, based on ideas such as erosion moving stones, etc.
2. Adjustments may be made further still, if judgement dictates it is necessary.

²⁹ See: Dwardu Cardona, and see also the Mayan traditions of Quetzlcoatl:

“It was in the year called one-reed. It is said that when he arrived at the sea, on the shore of the ocean, he stopped, cried, arranged his belongings, and got dressed in his finery, his turquoise mask, etc. And when he had entirely prepared himself, he himself set himself on fire, put himself into the flames And that is why it is called Tlatlayän, the place where Quetzalcöätl was burned. And they say that when he burned, his ashes rose up into the air, and there appeared, as they looked at it, all the rare [thunder]birds, which flew upwards; and there were to be seen in the sky... And after his ashes there [were all gone], then the heart of Quetzalcöätl rose up, And after his ashes there [were all gone], then the heart of Quetzalcöätl rose up, The old people said that it changed into the star that appears at dawn [Venus] according to what they say, it appeared when Quetzalcöätl died, so they called it Tlahuizcalpantëuctli (“Lord of the Dawn”). According to what they said, when he died, it was not seen for four days. [Did not radiate?] They said that then he went to dwell in the realm of the dead.” [ie, went towards the Otherworld, which we now know is beyond Hades/planet Uranus]

<http://pages.ucsd.edu/~dkjordan/nahuatl/ReadingQuetzalcoatl.html>

³⁰ +/- will not matter, nor will units. X is equatorial, Y is polar diameters.

Data³¹ relies on Diagrams A through E in scans after bibliography.

Table 3: Comparison data based on measurements

	Sun (km)	Jupiter	Saturn	Neptune
X	1,391,982.80	142,984.00	120,536.00	49,244.00
Y	1,391,972.80	133,709.00	108,728.00	48,682.00
X:Y	1.000007184	1.069367058	1.10860128	1.011544308
vs A	20.00%	14.45%	11.31%	19.08%
vs C	10.20%	3.98%	0.45%	9.17%
vs D	14.81%	8.91%	5.56%	13.83%
vs B1	7.14%	0.70%	-2.94%	6.07%
vs B2	12.50%	6.43%	3.00%	11.49%
vs B3	8.11%	1.73%	-1.87%	7.05%
vs E1	22.99%	17.65%	14.63%	22.10%
vs E2	10.26%	4.04%	0.52%	9.23%
vs E3	7.16%	0.72%	-2.92%	6.09%
vs E4	13.15%	7.13%	3.72%	12.15%
vs E5	12.31%	6.22%	2.78%	11.29%
vs E6	13.35%	7.34%	3.94%	12.35%
vs E7	8.73%	2.40%	-1.18%	7.68%
Uranus	Venus	Mars	Moon	Mercury
50,724.00	12,104.00	6,779.00	3,474.20	4,879.40
49,946.00	12,103.60	6,752.00	3,471.90	4,879.00
1.015576823	1.000033048	1.003998815	1.000662461	1.000081984
18.75%	20.00%	19.68%	19.95%	19.99%
8.81%	10.20%	9.85%	10.14%	10.20%
13.49%	14.81%	14.47%	14.76%	14.81%
5.70%	7.14%	6.77%	7.08%	7.14%
11.14%	12.50%	12.15%	12.44%	12.49%
6.68%	8.11%	7.74%	8.05%	8.10%
21.79%	22.99%	22.68%	22.94%	22.98%
8.87%	10.26%	9.91%	10.21%	10.26%
5.71%	7.16%	6.79%	7.10%	7.15%
11.80%	13.15%	12.80%	13.09%	13.14%
10.94%	12.30%	11.96%	12.25%	12.30%
12.00%	13.35%	13.00%	13.29%	13.34%
7.31%	8.73%	8.37%	8.67%	8.72%

³¹ <http://bit.ly/2UJwT95>

Table 4: Comparisons with Ramesses and Chia Stele

	Ramesses Stele	Ramesses II	Chia Stele	Average	A	C	D
X	0.4852	0.799	0.861	0.7150666667	5.75	12.25	6.75
Y	0.393	0.694	0.692	0.593	4.6	11	5.75
X:Y	1.23	1.15	1.24	1.21	1.20	1.22	1.21
Stand_Dev	2.99%						
vs A	-1.25%	-8.57%	-0.46%	-3.30%	0.00%	1.38%	0.69%
vs C	9.80%	3.27%	10.50%	7.97%	-1.40%	0.00%	-0.70%
vs D	1.98%	-5.12%	2.73%	-0.01%	-0.69%	0.70%	0.00%
vs E1	-5.18%	-12.79%	-4.37%	-7.31%	-8.05%	-6.55%	-7.30%
vs B3	11.86%	5.48%	12.54%	10.07%	9.45%	10.71%	10.08%
vs E2	9.74%	3.20%	10.43%	7.90%	7.28%	8.56%	7.92%
vs A2	-1.25%	-8.57%	-0.46%	-3.30%	-4.01%	-2.57%	-3.29%
vs A3	8.55%	1.93%	9.26%	6.69%	6.06%	7.36%	6.71%

Table 5: Diagram A-D measurements and ratios

	A	X:Y	B	X:Y	C	X:Y	D	X:Y
X1	5.75	1.25	4.2	1.076923077	12.25	1.113636364	6.75	1.173913043
Y1	4.6		3.9		11		5.75	
X2	7	1.129032258	3.6	1.142857143				
Y2	6.2		3.15					
X3	7	1.044776119	3.7	1.088235294				
Y3	6.7		3.4					

Table 6: Diagram E (the 'Flowering' Flare God)

	E	Ratios
X1	1.257	1.298553719
Y1	0.968	
X2	0.565	1.114398422
Y2	0.507	
X3	0.535	1.077108919
Y3	0.4967	
X4	0.654	1.151408451
Y4	0.568	
X5	0.6899	1.140330579
Y5	0.605	
X6	0.5491	1.154056326
Y6	0.4758	
X7	0.7891	1.09566787
Y7	0.7202	

Looking across the tables, the most clear diameter ratios are Saturnian. Second most are Jovian, and finally Uranus and *maybe* Neptune in diagram B appear, which tells us that this story **is** primarily the discussion from the Ramesses stele, which would date it from 5,000 YBP to 9,000 YBP, based on the Giza plateau being shown to have an Orion configuration 11,000 YBP to 13,000 YBP but the author, also using ratio methods in a separate study³² and also comparing with the motifs of Gobekli Tepe to confirm that the motifs on the stele concern the “vulture” (hawk³³) motif continuing to evolve (devolve?) into the story discussed in the stele.

Furthermore, there is some evidence that the **end** of Gobekli Tepe, with its famous T pillar the “Vulture Stone” is seen (because it is not at the bottom of the archaeological site which remains buried) at the boundary conditions 9,000 YBP to 10,000 YBP. A separate study of this pillar would satisfy the reader to the ratio theory (now a third site on our map) as it is around 1.25 as well.

Figure 6 - the Vulture Stone

Note that the egg on the stone has the same bulge as in Maputo diagrams, suggesting, again, the electrified lattice exclusion/exfoliation method of planet birth via ejection.³⁴

³² <https://www.researchgate.net/project/Great-Pyramids-of-Kentucky> [15]

³³ It should be noted that the 1.25 egg in the stele and Vulture Stone too are associated with Horus the Hawk, which is commonly associated with Jupiter and not Saturn. This could change the dating to a much newer era 3.5 kya - 5.5 kya

³⁴ Please note, however, that those in the southern hemisphere of the Earth saw it as out the vagina of a mother goddess, to birth the morning star, rather than out of a throat. Given our evidence of Earth flip from Chillicothe, this seems to make

Summary

In summary, the measurements show:

- ❖ Diagrams C, B3, and E7 are closest to satellite measurement of Saturn
- ❖ Diagrams B1 and E3 are very close to Jupiter
- ❖ But they are also almost passable for Neptune or Uranus, with Uranus being slightly better
- ❖ Diagrams A1, C, and D all represent the same ~1.21-1.25 ratio “egg motif” from the Ramesses Stele
- ❖ The stele specifically mentions this as the previous star-god
- ❖ The Chia stele is closest to the proper egg shape, and may be a better record, or it could be a fluke.
- ❖ **None** of the rocky bodies can be described as particularly excellent, save perhaps A3
- ❖ Rocky bodies tend to be nearly perfectly ratio’d (and round), so the egg motif **cannot** be a rocky body, such as Venus, Mars, or the Moon.
- ❖ Therefore in worldwide rock art motifs all egg archetypes must age previous to the Transition Period, and possibly the Megalithic Period, into the Archaic and beyond.
- ❖ The E diagram “flower” might be showing too many gas giant bodies, unless one is lost or is Planet 9, but it is possible that we are looking at a site that means something else, or is too eroded to be relied on.
- ❖ C, D, and A2 are also close to each other, enough to conclude A2 is probably Jupiter.
- ❖ A3 and the Ramesses II stele are very close to each other, and probably shows concordance.

Conclusions

In Kentucky the egg motif shows a much different ratio, with one site showing 1.4 and a lost major earthwork being of unknown ratio, but having an inward notch instead of outward. However, in 3 places from the other side of the prime meridian we see an agreement of the egg motif. It is entirely possible that the egg motif - Aten/Atum/Amen - is not the gas giant itself, but the plasma double layer around the ovoid dwarf star, and that the shape changed as the gas giants were birthed from it. It is also possible at times that the gas giant bodies merely aligned or approached, and this motif was collected. Or it could be a montage of the order of the gods, and the “two families” (described in the Vedas and the Norse traditions). But whatever it represents, it is surely the Clash of the Titans. It may also represent the birth of the gas giants, if that might also be the same event, it is not known.

The use of these sites at Maputo and Bakoni is to provide a southern hemispheric perspective, and a verification of the Middle Eastern vantage. As yet a comprehensive egg motif study of all world sites has not been compiled into a complete database of ratios. The author would call on all the readers and scientists studying in archaeo-astronomy, to help complete this collection and study, to result in a more comprehensive look which can be provided to modelers that might reconstruct the object in the sky, and a more specific timeline. The “egg series” will continue with discussions of the Kentucky motifs and the Vulture Stone, along with more searches from South America, China, etc. which may provide more clues as to the nature of the egg itself as either a double layer or the liquid metallic hydrogen, plasma, or gas surface of a dwarf star or gas giant, etc. Also, more analysis of Egyptian stele, including portions of the Ramesses stele not yet analyzed.

sense. However, rock art in Utah may actually indicate these are **two separate** exfoliation events. One in the Tepe/Archaic Period boundary, one in the Megalithic Period, memorialized by younger cultures (such as the Vikings or Aztecs)

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